

Use of Potassium Bromate : Bromination of Derivatives of Benzene

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Bromination of various derivatives of benzene using potassium bromate under acidic condition has been discussed.

CONSIDERABLE work has recently been done on the oxidation of metal ions¹ using potassium bromate; standard bromate-bromide solution has been used for the estimation of organic compounds possessing various functional groups² and by bromometric method^{3a} for cyclohexanoneoxime^{3b} and ascorbic acid^{3c}. Application of this reagent in acid media for the kinetic studies of the oxidation of diols⁴, α -hydroxy acids and α -hydroxy ketones^{5a}, secondary alcohols^{5b}, cycloalkanols in acetic acid^{5c} and in acetic acid-dilute sulphuric acid^{6a}, phenols^{6b}, primary alcohols^{6c}, D(+) glucose^{7a} and the thermal decomposition of potassium bromate^{7b} as well as aldehydes⁸ indicate the developing interest in this area. The Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction^{9a} has been thoroughly investigated^{9b-h}. Spectroscopic investigations⁹ⁱ, comparison of experiments with calculations^{9j} and oscillation reaction in oxalic acid-acetone substrate^{9k} have also been carried out.

In spite of the massive work done in the above areas, the application of bromate in synthetic organic chemistry is scanty. It has been used for oxidative bromination of methylxanthenes¹⁰ in acid medium forming 8-bromoderivatives, in oxidation of benzoins in caustic soda^{11a} or potassium carbonate solution^{11b} producing the benzoic acids and in generating a diazo-like species from 1,1-dialkylhydrazines¹² in acidic solution. Sodium bromate in acetic acid has been reported to be an excellent reagent for the oxidation of 1-bromo-triptycenehydroquinone to the corresponding quinone derivatives¹³. Boranes have been reacted with bromate¹⁴. The syntheses of the aromatic sulphonyl bromides from sulphonyl hydrazides¹⁵ utilised either the bromate-bromide mixture or bromate alone in acidic solution for the oxidative bromination. Sodium bromate and hydrobromic acid brominated 2-substituted-4-acetoquinolines in acetic acid solution¹⁶ and triphenylphosphinebromocarbomethoxymethylene was prepared by Märkl^{17a} using potassium bromate and bromide in the usual way. Standardised bromate-bromide solution has also been used in carbon tetrachloride solution for the preparation of cyclopentamethylenedibromostannane from cyclopentamethylene-

diphenylstannane^{17b}. Derivatives of the thioglycolic acid have been oxidised to the sulphoxides utilising bromate-bromide mixture¹⁸ in acidic solution. Recently Tse-Lok Ho has reported^{19a} the oxidation of aryl-methanols to the carbonyl compounds in excellent yield using bromate in dilute acetonitrile with ammonium cerium(IV) nitrate as catalyst. Similar treatment oxidised hydroquinones and sulphides^{19b} as well as cleaved alkyl and silyl ethers^{19c}. Derbyshire and Waters²⁰ effected cationoid bromination of benzoic acid in the presence of elemental bromine with potassium bromate in sulphuric acid at room temperature.

It was previously observed²¹ that potassium bromate can incorporate bromine in the aromatic nucleus^{21b} in a predictable way when the reaction was carried out in boiling (4-8 *N*) sulphuric acid with or without the assistance of acetic acid as solvent. It was expected that bromination with bromate was novel but later it was known that Kraft²², in 1875, had reported the bromination of benzene at room temperature with bromate and 33% sulphuric acid producing bromobenzene in 70-80% yield. Kraft's method has been repeated several times in these laboratories but the yield of crude bromobenzene was never higher than 15%. It has also been noted that addition of mercuric acetate in the reaction mixture^{21b} increased the yield of 1,4-dibromo-benzene which may be lowered by using excess of benzene. The Derbyshire and Waters' method of bromination²⁰ was effective even in 1 *N* sulphuric acid and acetic acid mixture but totally ineffective in acetic acid medium. The nascent bromine, generated during the oxidation of organic substrate in acetic acid, could not brominate the aromatic nucleus in absence of strong ring activators. *m*-Dinitrobenzene and *m*-nitrobenzoic acid did not undergo bromination by this method. Boiling 4 *N* sulphuric acid could decompose potassium bromate into bromine. During the bromination of derivatives of benzene by the present method the reaction mixture assumed a beautiful orange-red colour at the beginning which gradually faded with the progress of reaction. From the regioselective nature of the bromination by this method the free radical mechanism may be ignored and the reaction should proceed

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through an electrophilic species, be it a bromonium ion, Br^+ , or a dioxobromonium ion, O_2Br^+ , the action of the latter, if formed at all is not apparent. It may be proposed that by the action of boiling sulphuric acid on potassium bromate an infinitesimally small quantity of elemental bromine is set free which generates Br^+ as suggested by Derbyshire and Waters²⁰. However, any comment on this reaction mechanism warrants further investigation.

Experimental²¹

The nmr spectra have been taken mostly in 90MHz and expressed in δ ppm. GLC was carried out with a Hewlett Packard 5730A gas chromatograph with flame ionisation detector using H. P. recorder model 7127A. HPLC was carried out with Waters Associate's model using a column of μ Bondapak. The identity of each solid product was established either through m.m.p. with authentic samples or elemental analysis, neutral equivalent (N. E.) and spectral data.

A. Bromobenzene²²: To a mixture of pure benzene (12 g) and potassium bromate (24 g) dilute sulphuric acid (33% by volume) was added with shaking when the reaction mixture became warm with evolution of bromine vapour. It was cooled under tap water (30-35°) and left at the room temperature for sixteen hours. The mixture was diluted with water and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene. The organic layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a dark residue (8 g) was obtained which was distilled to furnish bromobenzene^{21b} (3.6 g, 15%), b.p. 150-170°, leaving a high boiling tarry residue (3.0 g).

B. 3-Bromobenzoic acid²⁰: (a) To a solution of benzoic acid (6 g) in acetic acid (25 ml) a solution of bromine (3 ml) in acetic acid (6 ml) was added followed by potassium bromate (8 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 30 mins. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto water followed by extraction with chloroform. The organic layer was washed with sodium bisulphite solution, water and dried. On removal of the solvent unreacted benzoic acid was obtained (5.8 g, m.p. 120°) responding faintly to Beilstein test for halogen. (b) A mixture of benzoic acid (6 g), bromine (8 g), potassium bromate (8 g), acetic acid (100 ml) and sulphuric acid (1 N 100 ml) was left at room temperature for 20 hrs, then worked up with chloroform to yield crude bromobenzoic acid (7.4 g, m.p. 90-95°) which responded strongly to Beilstein test. (c) In the similar method a mixture of benzoic acid (6 g), acetic acid (100 ml), bromine (8 g), potassium bromate (8 g) and sulphuric acid (4 N 100 ml) was left at room temperature for 20 hrs with occasional shaking. The reaction mixture containing large amount of precipitated solid was worked up with chloroform in the aforementioned manner to isolate faintly yellow acid (9.5 g, m.p. 135-137°) which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol furnished pure 3-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 155°.

C. Bromotoluene: To a boiling mixture of toluene (27.6 g), acetic acid (200 ml), sulphuric acid (8 N 170 ml) a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g in

170 ml warm water) was added dropwise in course of thirty minutes. There was not much evolution of bromine and the mixture was refluxed for another hr. The usual working up with chloroform followed by removal of the solvent gave a residue which on distillation furnished pale yellow crude bromotoluene (11.6 g, 68%), b.p. 175-176°^{23a}. This material on oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate afforded an acidic material in 50% yield which melted at 190° and on several crystallisations from aqueous ethanol gave colourless crystals of 4-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 240°^{23b}. GLC of the crude bromotoluene was unable to distinguish the isomers but HPLC identified it as a mixture of 2-bromotoluene (25%) and 4-bromotoluene (75%).

D. Bromoanisole: A mixture of freshly distilled anisole (21.6 g), acetic acid (200 ml) and sulphuric acid (8 N 170 ml) was refluxed and a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g in 170 ml warm water) was added dropwise to it. Boiling was continued for 35 mins and the reaction mixture, after the usual work up with chloroform afforded crude bromoanisole (13.6 g, 72%), b.p. 82-83°/3 mm^{23c} as pale yellow oil. GLC indicated 40% *ortho*-bromoanisole and 60% *para*-bromoanisole in this product.

E. 3-Bromonitrobenzene: In a similar method a mixture of nitrobenzene (12.3 g), sulphuric acid (8 N 170 ml) and potassium bromate (16.7 g in 170 ml water) was heated under reflux for 10 hrs. Usual work up furnished the unreacted starting material b.p. 82°/3 mm followed by 3-bromonitrobenzene (5.5 g, 27%) b.p. 110°/3 mm which became yellowish solid on standing. On crystallisation from ethanol this material gave colourless flakes of 3-bromonitrobenzene, m.p. 56°^{23d}.

F. 3-Bromobenzonitrile: The yield of the brominated product from phenyl cyanide was 27% in the general procedure, so the following modified method was adopted to improve the yield. A mixture of distilled phenyl cyanide (20.6 g), acetic acid (150 ml), sulphuric acid (8 N 250 ml) and potassium bromate (25 g in 250 ml warm water) was left at room temperature (30-35°) for 16 hrs followed by heating under reflux for 3 hrs. Usual working up of the reaction mixture furnished a colourless liquid (7.3 g, 40%), b.p. 96°/3 mm which solidified on standing. Crystallisation of this material from dilute ethanol yielded colourless crystals, m.p. 39-40°^{23e}, which on acid hydrolysis afforded 3-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 155°^{23b}. Small amounts of benzoic acid and 3-bromobenzoic acid are also formed during the bromination step.

G. 4-Bromobenzanilide: To a boiling mixture of benzanilide (5 g), sulphuric acid (8 N 42 ml) and acetic acid (100 ml) a solution of potassium bromate (4.2 g in 45 ml warm water) was added dropwise in course of half an hr and boiling was continued for another hr. The dark brown reaction mixture deposited a brown solid on cooling (2.2 g; 32%) which on crystallisation from ethanol yielded colourless flakes, m.p. 198°^{23e}. This material on hydrolysis furnished benzoic acid and *p*-bromoaniline, m.p. 66°. The latter on benzylation furnished the starting 4-bromobenzanilide.

H. 5-Bromo-2-hydroxybenzoic acid: To a boiling mixture of salicylic acid (27.4 g), sulphuric acid (8 N

170 ml) and acetic acid (100 ml) a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g in 170 ml warm water) was added dropwise in course of 25 mins and refluxing was continued for further 5 mins. The dark brown reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the resulting crude acid (30.2 g, the increase in weight indicating 35% bromination) was esterified with ethanol and sulphuric acid and worked up in the usual way to furnish (i) low boiling fraction (10 g), b.p. 82-83°/2 mm, [δ (CCl₄), 1.2 (t; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃), 4.37 (q; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃), 6.77 (H_s; d, d, d; J=2, 6, 6 H_Z), 7.38 (H₄; d, d, d; J=3, 8, 8H_Z), 7.77 (H₆; d, d; J=3, 8 H_Z) and 7.90 (H₈[†]; d, d; J=3, 8 H_Z), which on hydrolysis with alcoholic potassium hydroxide produced salicylic acid, m.p. 155° and (ii) desired material (6.0 g), b.p. 130-135°/3 mm. [δ (CCl₄), 1.45 (t; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃), 4.40 (q; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃), 6.82 (H_s; d; J=9H_Z), 7.47 (H₄; d, d; J=3, 9H_Z) and 7.87 (H₆; d; J=3H_Z)] which on alkaline hydrolysis in the usual way furnished 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzoic acid, m.p. 166-167°^{23c} after one crystallisation from dilute ethanol.

I. **4-Bromohydrocinnamic acid**: A mixture of β -phenyl-propionic acid (4.4 g), acetic acid (50 ml) and sulphuric acid (8 N 50 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (5 g in 50 ml hot water) was slowly added to it. The reaction was continued for further 1 hr. The cold reaction mixture was worked up with chloroform in the usual way to yield the crude bromo-acid (6.0 g) which was esterified with ethanol and sulphuric acid to furnish crude ester (7.0 g). It was distilled at 154-156°/4 mm as light yellow oil (5.0 g), nmr spectrum (60MH_z) [δ (CCl₄), 1.2 (3H, t; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃), 2.7 (4H, complex *m*-CH₂-CH₂-), 4.0 (2H, q; J=7H_Z, -CH₂-CH₃) and 7.17 (4H, complex *m*, aromatic)]. The HPLC indicated it to be a mixture. A crude acid was obtained on alkaline hydrolysis which furnished pure 4-bromohydrocinnamic acid, m.p. 136°^{23f} in 20% yield on several crystallisations from dilute ethanol. The N. E. of the acid was 232±5.

J. **4-Bromocinnamic acid**: A solution of potassium bromate (25 g in 250 ml hot water) was added dropwise to a boiling mixture of cinnamic acid (15 g), acetic acid (150 ml) and sulphuric acid (8 N 250 ml) in course of 30 mins and refluxing was continued for further 1 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the crude acid (25 g) was esterified with ethanol and sulphuric acid. The ester was worked up including washing with sodium bicarbonate and distilled to furnish the following fractions, i) b.p. 92-100°/6 mm, (3.1 g) which on alkaline hydrolysis yielded benzoic acid, m.p. 122°, ii) b.p. 135-150°/6 mm, (5 g) which on alkaline hydrolysis gave the desired 4-bromocinnamic acid, m.p. 253°^{23g}, N. E. 222±5 and iii) b.p. 160-185°/6 mm, (6.1 g) which was not investigated.

K. **Bromination of phenylacetic acid**: To a boiling mixture of phenylacetic acid (13.6 g), acetic acid (100 ml) and sulphuric acid (8 N 170 ml) was added a solution of potassium bromate (17 g in 170 ml warm water) in course of 20 mins and heating was continued for further 1 hr followed by work up with chloroform in the usual way. The crude acid (21 g) thus obtained

was esterified and worked up to yield a colourless oil, b.p. 150-157°/0 mm (18 g). The latter on alkaline hydrolysis furnished an acid which crystallised from hot water, m.p. 94-98°, contained bromine and exhibited N. E. 210±5 indicating itself to be a mixture of *ortho* and *para*-bromophenyl acetic acid^{23h} which could not be separated into pure components.

L. **3-Bromobenzophenone and 3,3'-dibromobenzophenone**: A mixture of benzophenone (9.1 g), acetic acid (150 ml) and sulphuric acid (8N 130 ml) was heated under reflux and an aqueous solution of potassium bromate (12.5 g in 130 ml warm water) was added to it dropwise in course of 30 mins and boiling was continued for further 1 hr. The cold reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the residue on distillation furnished fraction (i) as colourless mobile oil (5.5 g), b.p. 160-175°/4 mm and fraction (ii) as a viscous oil (3.8 g), b.p. 185-195°/4 mm. The fraction (i) became solid on standing which was crystallised from ethanol to furnish colourless crystals of 3-bromobenzophenone, m.p. 75°^{23b}, (Found C, 59.26; H, 3.32; C₁₃H₉BrO requires C, 59.38; H, 3.44%). Major signals in mass spectrum at m/e 262, 260(M⁺), 185, 183 (C₇H₄BrO⁺), 157, 155 (C₆H₄Br⁺), 105 (C₇H₅O⁺), 77 (C₆H₅⁺) and 51 (C₄H₃⁺). It gave an oxime, m.p. 132°^{23b} and an orange 2,4-D.N.P., m.p. 239°(d) (Found N, 13.01, C₁₉H₁₃BrN₄O₄ requires N, 12.69%). The fraction (ii) immediately became solid which was crystallised from petroleum ether (40-60°) to yield colourless crystals of 3,3'-dibromobenzophenone, m.p. 141°²⁴, (Found C, 46.24; H, 2.54; C₁₃H₈Br₂O requires C, 45.88; H, 2.35%). Major signals in mass spectrum at m/e 338, 340, 342 (M⁺), 185, 183 (C₇H₄BrO⁺), 157, 155 (C₆H₄Br⁺), signals at m/e 105, 77 and 51 were virtually absent.

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